

Free Particle Action, Lorentz Invariants and Geodesics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 27, 2022

In a previous note (1) we showed that a free particle Action = $\int L dt$ Lagrangian, $-m_0 c \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ (relativistic) or $\int \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 dt$ (nonrelativistic) may be written as the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ if one sets $v=x/t$ with x and t being independent. In this note we wish to compare these expressions in terms of geodesics. In particular, it is shown in (2) that Lagrange's equation yields a geodesic i.e. a straight line solution which is a geodesic in a flat space.

If one writes $v=x/t$ it seems one already assumes a geodesic or motion in a straight line as in the case of Lorentz transformation. For example, if one has a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$ then when viewed from a system moving at constant v (assumed to be moving in a straight line), x' and t' have the property that $x'/t' = v = \text{constant}$. Thus motion along a geodesic (straight line in flat space) seems to be "built-in" to special relativity. This result, however, should map into the Action/Lagrangian result which also predicts straight line motion. One may ask: What sort of special relativistic expression containing x and t should one write? The expression should contain E and p as well as x and t and so a dot product seems like a natural choice. This choice is identical to the free particle Lagrangian (relativistic or nonrelativistic) if one manually uses $v=x/t$ i.e. forces straight line motion into the Lagrangian so one no longer needs to use the Lagrangian equation $d/dt dL/dv - dL/dx = 0$ for a free particle. One may note that $p = dL/dv$ or $dA/dx = p$ (for x and t independent) where $A=Lt$ so the term px is consistent with Lagrangian theory and a Lorentz invariant.

The Lagrangian and Motion Along a Geodesics i.e. Straight Line in Free Space

A Lagrangian is usually defined as $L=T-V$ where T is kinetic energy and V the potential. For a free particle, one has $V(x)=0$. The equation of motion follows from the Lagrangian equation:

$$d/dt dL/dv - dL/dx = 0 \text{ (for no constraints) with } p=dL/dv \text{ ((1))}$$

In (2) it is shown that ((1)) predicts motion in a straight line between two points in the x - y plane if one assumes $y(x)$ and replaces t with x in ((1)). In particular:

$$Ds = \sqrt{dx^2 + dy^2} = dx \sqrt{1 + dy/dx dy/dx} = dx f(y') \text{ where } y' = dy/dx \text{ ((2))}$$

Using $f(y') = \sqrt{1+y'^2}$ in ((1)) with t replaced by x yields:

$$d/dx \{ (1+y'^2)^{-1/2} y' \} = 0 \text{ so } y' = \text{constant or } y=mx+b \text{ ((3))}$$

((3)) is the solution of a straight line which is a geodesic in a flat space.

Thus the Lagrange equation ((1)) predicts motion along a straight line for a free particle with rest mass.

Lorentz Transformations

Interestingly, a Lorentz transformation also assumes motion along a geodesic i.e. in a straight line as one considers flat space. In special relativity one has a frame moving at a constant velocity v in a straight line because one chooses a distance coordinate along the straight line velocity vector distance. Thus a Lorentz transformation is compatible with the straight line solution given by the Lagrangian equation ((1)). To see the Lorentz transformation behaviour more clearly consider a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$. The Lorentz matrix:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g & vg \\ vg & g \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{where } g = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Yields: } x' = vg t_0 \quad \text{and } t' = g t_0 \quad \text{so } x'/t' = v = \text{constant} \quad ((5))$$

It is already assumed that motion is in a straight line along x' i.e. along a geodesic. Thus special relativity (Lorentz transformation) contains the same information that a free particle Lagrangian does i.e. a constant velocity v and straight line motion. In particular one may ask:

What happens if one takes the relativistic or nonrelativistic free particle action $= \int L dt$ and replaces v with x/t i.e. inserts the "straight line" (geodesic) motion result.

In such a case one no longer needs the Lagrangian equation ((1)) because the result i.e. motion in a straight line is already contained in replacing v with x/t . We argue the result should be compatible with special relativity which also assumes straight line motion. Special relativity contains 4-vectors such as (x,t) and (p,E) which are particularly relevant to free particle motion. As a result, one might speculate that the action $= \int L dt$ becomes the Lorentz invariant $-\int Et + px$. This result follows for both the relativistic and nonrelativistic actions i.e.

$$A = -\int m_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} dt \rightarrow -\int Et + px \quad \text{when } v \text{ is replaced with } x/t \quad \text{and } x \text{ and } t \text{ are considered independent}$$

$$A = \int \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 dt \rightarrow -\int Et + px \quad \text{when } v \text{ is replaced with } x/t \quad ((6))$$

One may note that: $p = dL/dv$ so $dA/dx = \int dt dL/dx = \int dt dL/dv \cdot d/dx (x/t)$ For x and t independent one has $p = dA/dx$ which is consistent with $-\int Et + px$.

As a result, it is not an accident that the classical free particle action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) is equivalent to the Lorentz invariant $-\int Et + px$. It seems that the equivalence is based on the idea of a free particle traveling along a geodesic i.e. a straight line in free space.

Photon versus Particle with Rest Mass

The above arguments were made for a particle with rest mass. The Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, however, applies to any particle i.e. one with nonzero rest mass or one with zero rest mass, e.g. a photon. In addition motion along a geodesic i.e. straight line motion holds for both a particle with rest mass and for a photon (Fermat's principle). Thus $-Et+px$ has straight line motion built-in (for x and t being independent) and applies to both a photon and a particle with rest mass. In the case of a photon: $d(-Et+px) = 0$ so $dx/dt = E/p$ and $dx/dt=c$ in a vacuum. This result does not hold for a particle with mass.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the Lagrange equation for a free particle describes motion in a straight line as shown in (2). The relativistic Action is $-m_0 \int dt \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and the nonrelativistic $\int m_0 v dt$. On the other hand, special relativity assumes motion in a straight line i.e. along a geodesic in flat space. In particular if one has a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$ it transforms to x' and t' such that $x'/t' = v = \text{constant}$. Motion is considered to be along the straight line vector of the moving frame. Thus Lagrange's equation and special relativity both contain the same information for a free particle, namely constant v motion along a straight line. Thus they should be formally equivalent. If one takes the classical action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) i.e. $L dt$ and replaces v with x/t , i.e. directly assumes straight line motion, one no longer needs the Lagrange differential equation. One may speculate that this result should yield a "special relativistic" result containing the 4-vectors (x,t) and (p,E) . Furthermore this result should be equivalent to $dL/dt = p$. This suggests the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$. Then $dA/dx = p = t dL/dx = t dL/dv d/dx (x/t)$ with x and t being independent so $p = dA/dx$. Thus the main idea is that of motion in a straight line i.e. along a geodesic in flat space. One may note that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ applies to both a photon and particle with a rest mass, but a photon also travels along a straight line (Fermat's principle) so there is consistency.

References

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